

Researchers' perceived value of big data curation

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to understand the value of big data curation in a professional context. Researchers' understanding of big data curation is critical to promptly preparing data for future use and curating professionals preparing. The literature analysis suggests that big data researchers acknowledge the value of curation in staying abreast of technology and data quality, but social aspects (e.g., legal and ethical issues) are less recognized.

KEYWORDS

Big data, data curation

INTRODUCTION

The importance of data curation, both as a field of study and as a professional practice, is well recognized across different disciplines (Shankar et al., 2021). Data curation makes data findable and accessible, provides the ability to trace its history and changes (provenance), and classifies data by its characteristics (e.g., public vs. private, open vs. proprietary, and legal and ethical implications). With this recognition, a growing number of libraries have provided data curation and management services for researchers (Yoon & Schultz, 2017). While data curation professionals, such as data curators and data librarians, play a significant role in data curation, collaboration with researchers who are data producers is still important, as these roles often need to work together to take time-appropriate actions when data are created and to provide contexts for studies and documentation. Having a shared value of data curation between researchers and data curation professionals (e.g., metadata, documentation, storage, etc.) is thus important for maintaining the value of data and delivering services that align with practical needs (Johnston et al., 2018).

Big data curation has recently become essential and apparent in various research fields, such as medicine, environmental science, and urban planning (Reinhalter & Wittmann, 2014). Libraries have been involved in data management services suited for data-intensive applications and services, but they are still in their infancy (Lyon, 2012; Martinez-Uribe & Macdonald, 2008). Additionally, many efforts have been based on big data characteristics, such as volume, velocity, and variety (Chao et al., 2015; Siddiqi et al., 2016), rather than on a holistic approach to understanding big data's curation lifecycle. A recent study presented a curation framework specifically for big data that can be a useful tool for developing big data curation programs; however, it also argued that the current landscape of big data curation is unclear regarding who contributes what curation actions, what value big data researchers see in data curation, and how their perceived value and associated needs align with those in identified curation actions (Yoon et al., 2022).

This poster reports a primary finding from the current study, aiming to understand big data researchers' perceptions and perspectives on the value of big data curation and its significance. This is the first part of a multi-step study to understand big data curation practices by following big data lifecycles and developing big data curation services at libraries. While researchers' perceptions and views on big data curation and its value may not always align with those of curation professionals, mutual views on necessary curation actions will help build trusting relationships between data producers (researchers) and curators and further develop curation services at institutions.

METHODS

To understand big data researchers' view (i.e., those who produce and/or use big data for their research), the project team first conducted a systematic review, which will be used in the next step of the study (survey). The goal of the systematic review was to search for articles that discussed any big data curation-relevant activities conducted or suggested by big data researchers during their research cycles. While there were not many studies solely discussing the value of big data curation as a topic, many that utilized big data presented issues or problems associated with big data curation that were connected to the discussion on its value.

Only journal articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters published after 2012 and written in English were included in the keyword search in three major databases—Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and EBSCOhost. Five different search terms were adopted: “big data curation,” “big data management,” “big data challenges,” “big data problems,” and “big data issues.” Because the term “big data curation” is not well adopted in all disciplines that may utilize big data research, the term “big data management” was also employed because it is often used when addressing data curation issues. We also utilized “big data challenges,” “big data problems,” and “big data issues” because these terms often reveal the value of big data curation. A total of 492 articles were collected from this initial search. Article quality was manually assessed based on the abstract, and irrelevant articles, duplicates, and low-

quality articles were removed during the first assessment. Next, the project team analyzed the data using a pre-developed protocol, including the disciplines of the authors, the definition of big data curation, the significance of big data curation, challenges, and actions relevant to data curation (e.g., documentation, metadata, storage, and quality control). Quality assessments were continued during this process, resulting in 105 articles remaining for inclusion in the final analysis. Once our analysis was finished, we inductively coded, searching for emerging themes under the bigger theme of big data curation values and significance. The final analysis captured 85 excerpts about big data curation values from 13 codes created during the iterative process (see the next section).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The various research areas utilizing big data included in this study comprised computer science, business, engineering, geography, economics, earth science, medicine, archaeology, architecture, astronomy, psychology, education, and sociology. This wide array of fields demonstrates the growing use of big data in various disciplines.

Table 1 presents the various values of big data curation recognized by big data researchers during their big data use. The most commonly acknowledged value of big data curation was addressing new technology and the data revolution (31.7%). Researchers have argued that big data curation is different from traditional data management due to the characteristics of big data (e.g., it is heterogeneous and unstructured) and because, currently, there is no system to fully support big data curation. Data curation as a way to improve data quality (15.3%) and maximizing the value of data (14.1%) were the next most recognized in terms of the value of big data curation. Researchers noted the need to “define principles and scalable approaches for coping with data quality issues” through the data management activity routine. Furthermore, they recognized that “because data exists does not mean it is valuable” and that big data curation is critical to a solution to the “data rich, information poor” problem. Several actions known to be relevant to data curation were also mentioned, such as data usability (5.9%), data interoperability (3.5%), and organization (2.4%).

Table 1. Recognized value of big data curation (n = 85)

Interestingly, but not surprisingly, few social aspects of data curation value were recognized by big data researchers, such as addressing legal and ethical issues (2.4%) and being compliant with data governance and policy (3.5%). In addition, many recognized values of big data curation focus on current use. While there were five excerpts about big data curation contributing to its future use (5.9%), only two directly mentioned the value of long-term preservation, which is a critical function of data curation.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STUDY

This study revealed that researchers perceived a high value to existing data which is integral to defining principles and scalable strategies for big data curation. Our next step is to survey big data researchers to confirm our findings and explore any unaddressed perceptions from the literature. The results from these two studies will be used to design the following research to understand big data curation practices at different levels (individuals and institutions) and to develop big data curation services.

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